

Extraction of Tris (Oxalato) Chromate(III) from Mineral Acid Solutions

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Manuscript received 22 July 1977, accepted 21 November 1977

Extraction of tris (oxalato) chromate(III) into trilaurylamine from mineral acid solutions has been studied. The extractions from hydrochloric, sulphuric and orthophosphoric acid solutions are quantitative while they are partial from nitric acid solutions; the extraction from perchloric acid is negligible. The effect of diluents and various anions on the extraction and the composition of the extracted species have been investigated. The mechanism of extraction of the metal complex is discussed in terms of the competition between various anions and the metal complex.

THE extraction of oxalate complexes of group VIII metals by long chain amines has been reported¹. Although the extraction of chromium in the hexavalent state into various ion association systems is studied by several workers²⁻⁴, not much is known about the liquid-liquid extraction of chromium in the trivalent state. The survey of literature on the extraction of chromium(III) into ion association systems indicates that most of the work is carried out by complexation with halides⁵ and with a few aminopolycarboxylic acids⁶⁻⁹. The present communication describes the studies on the extraction of tris (oxalato) chromate(III) into trilaurylamine from mineral acid solutions.

Experimental

Materials: Trilaurylamine (TLA) supplied as gift by M/S General Mills Inc., Kankakee, Illinois, was used as such without any further purification.

Potassium tris (oxalato) chromate(III) labelled with ⁵¹Cr was prepared by the method reported by Brauer¹⁰. Tracer was supplied in the form of sodium chromate in isotonic saline solution (sp. activity 15 mCi/mg) by Isotope Division, B.A.R.C., Bombay. The purity of the product was checked by analysis (Calculated for K₃Cr(C₂O₄)₃ · 3 H₂O : Cr, 10.67%; Oxalate, 54.17%; Found : Cr, 10.78%; Oxalate, 53.71%).

The absorption spectrum of the complex agreed well with that reported¹¹ with maxima at 420 nm ($\epsilon_{obs} = 95.0$; $\epsilon_{calc} = 97.0$) and 570 nm ($\epsilon_{obs} = 74.0$; $\epsilon_{calc} = 75.0$). It was observed that the complex was stable in different acid media for reasonable periods of time at the concentrations used in the study. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade or purified according to standard methods.

Equipment: Model SC600 γ -ray spectrometer with a single channel analyser (Electronics Corporation of India Ltd.) in conjunction with a 3" well type NaI (TI) crystal (Nuclear Chicago) was used for γ activity

measurements. The absorption spectrum was recorded using a Unicam SP600 Spectrophotometer.

Procedure: Since the amines act as extractants only in the form of amine salts^{1,2}, the organic phase (10 ml) was first preequilibrated with a 0.25 M solution of the corresponding acid for converting the amine to the amine salt. This is followed by equilibration with 10 ml of the aqueous phase containing appropriate concentrations of the metal complex and mineral acid for about five minutes. This was found sufficient to ensure maximum extraction. The two phases were then separated by allowing the mixture to settle for five minutes or by centrifuging. Equal aliquots of each phase were used to count the activity and the distribution coefficient (k_d) calculated using the equation,

$$k_d = \frac{\text{Counts/min. in the organic phase}}{\text{Counts/min. in the aqueous phase}}$$

The extractions were repeated for establishing reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

Effect of Preequilibration of Amine:

The effect of preequilibration of TLA on the extraction of the metal complex was studied by carrying out extractions using free base amine and amine preequilibrated with respective acids. The preequilibration with hydrochloric, sulphuric, nitric and phosphoric acid solutions improved extraction. A decrease in extraction is observed in preequilibration with perchloric acid (Table 1). The order of preference for anions is thus $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} \approx \text{PO}_4^{3-}$ which is similar to that with anion exchange resins¹³.

Extraction of the Metal Complex as a Function of Acidity:

There is no change in k_d upto 0.1 M acid beyond which a gradual fall is observed in the case of sulphuric

TABLE 1—PERCENTAGE EXTRACTION OF TRIS (OXALATO) CHROMATE (III) BY TLA.

[Cr(OX) ₃] ³⁻ =0.005 M Preequilibrated acid	[TLA]=0.025 M Percentage extraction
—	35.2
HClO ₄	28.9
HCl	78.4
H ₂ SO ₄	99.9
H ₃ PO ₄	99.9
HNO ₃	41.3

and orthophosphoric acid solutions. The extractions are quantitative upto 0.1 M sulphuric and phosphoric acid solutions, while they are quantitative and independent of acidity upto 0.001 M in the case of hydrochloric acid. On the other hand the extraction is partial from nitric acid solution with a rapid fall in *k_d* with the increase in acidity even at concentrations < 0.05 M. In contrast the extraction from perchloric acid solutions is negligible not exceeding 5% upto 0.005 M acid. Further it is possible to strip the metal complex from the organic phase with perchloric, nitric and hydrochloric acid solutions (0.1 M). On the other hand stripping does not occur with sulphuric and phosphoric acid solutions.

Composition of the Extracted Species :

The composition of the extracted species in hydrochloric, sulphuric and orthophosphoric acid solutions are determined by the extraction isotherm method¹⁴ and the distribution ratio method¹⁵. In the extraction isotherm method the limiting ratio of amine to the metal complex was found to be 3 : 1 (the acidity being 0.05 M with respect to sulphuric and phosphoric acids and 0.0005 M with respect to hydrochloric acid) in the distribution ratio method plots of log *k_d* vs log [TLA] in the three acid media gave straight lines with slope values of 3.0 indicating that the amine exists as monomer in chloroform with the amine/metal complex mole ratio of 3.0.

Effect of Anions on the Extraction of the Metal Complex from HCl Medium :

The extraction of the anionic metal complexes and the relative competition between the anionic metal complex and other anions for the protonated amine can be explained in terms of the equilibrium constant (*K_e*) during competition¹⁶

$$K_e = \frac{[R_3NHCl]_{(org)}^m [R_3NHX]_{(org)}^n}{[Cl^-]_{(aq)}^m [X^-]_{(aq)}^n k_d}$$

where X⁻ is the added anion, *m* and *n* represent the number of chloride ions and added anions respectively used to replace the metal complex from the extractant.

A negative slope (*n*) for log *k_d* vs log [anion] plot would indicate the number of anions competing with the chloride ion to replace metal complex from the organic phase. (Fig. 1). The value of *n* at any concentration of the anion indicates the number of anions competing at that concentration. The effect of anions ClO₄⁻, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ (source of the ions being the sodium salts) are given in Table 2, from which it can be seen that the univalent anions ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻ and Cl⁻ have greater affinity while SO₄²⁻ shows less affinity for the amine. The effect of SO₄²⁻ is negligible when

Fig. 1. Effect of added anions on the extraction of tris (oxalato) chromate(III) into TLA (HCl medium). [Cr(OX)₃]³⁻=0.005 M, [TLA]=0.025 M, [HCl]=0.0005 M. ○—○ Effect of perchlorate ion. Δ—Δ Effect of chloride ion. ×—× Effect of nitrate ion. □—□ Effect of sulphate ion.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ADDED ANION ON THE EXTRACTION OF TRIS (OXALATO) CHROMATE (III) INTO TLA (HCl MEDIUM).

	[Cr(OX) ₃] ³⁻ =0.005 M	[HCl]=0.001 M	[TLA]=0.025 M	
n	ClO ₄ ⁻ (M)	Cl ⁻ (M)	NO ₃ ⁻ (M)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (M)
1.	7.0 × 10 ⁻³	4.2 × 10 ⁻²	1.15 × 10 ⁻¹	—
2.	1.7 × 10 ⁻²	6.2 × 10 ⁻²	2.70 × 10 ⁻¹	—
3.	3.3 × 10 ⁻²	1.1 × 10 ⁻¹	4.60 × 10 ⁻¹	—

compared with the other anions. With Na₃PO₄ there is a decrease in extraction even at very low concentrations. It is observed that addition of Na₃PO₄ to the metal complex resulted in the formation of substituted metal

phosphate complex¹⁷. Hence the observed decrease in extraction cannot be attributed to the competition by the PO₄³⁻ ion. This effect of anions is thus similar to the effect of preequilibration on the extraction.

On the basis of these results the extraction of tris(oxalato)-chromate(III) by TLA from mineral acid media may be described in terms of the formation of protonated amine (R₃NH⁺) on preequilibration with the mineral acid which then extracts (or exchanges) the metal complex from the aqueous phase. The mechanism of extraction may therefore be represented as

The dissimilar extraction trends from various acid systems observed point to the possibility of the relative competition between the anion of the acid and the metal complex to the protonated amine with all acid systems excepting phosphoric acid which alters the nature of the complex¹⁷.

Effect of Diluents

Besides chloroform other diluents used in the present study are xylene, benzene, toluene, carbontetrachloride, dichloromethane, cyclohexane, heptane and nitrobenzene and a mixture of cyclohexanol and cyclohexane with relatively high dielectric constant. It can be seen from the Table 3 that the effect of the diluents on the extraction is profound. This behaviour can apparently be considered to be a function of the dielectric constant of the diluent. But the parallelism between the

percentage extraction and the dielectric constant is not strictly observed. For example chloroform ($\epsilon=4.8$) and nitrobenzene ($\epsilon=36.1$) behave similarly. Butcher and Diamond¹⁸ reported that in general the higher the dielectric constant of the diluent the better the extraction with an exception in the case of chloroform. They attributed the greater extraction in chloroform when compared to the diluents having higher dielectric constant to its hydrogen bonding tendency with the anion of the ammonium salt. In the present case also the behaviour of chloroform can be attributed to this property.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Mr. N. R. Anipindi for his assistance.

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TABLE 3—PERCENTAGE EXTRACTION OF TRIS(OXALATO) CHROMATE (III) WITH TLA IN DIFFERENT DILUENTS (HCl MEDIUM)

Diluent	[Cr(OX) ₃] ³⁻ = 0.005 M	
	[TLA] = 0.025 M	Percentage extraction HCl 0.005 M
Cyclohexane	2.02	20.4
Carbontetrachloride	2.24	21.8
Benzene	2.28	39.5
Xylene	2.37	38.2
Heptane	4.30	92.2
Chloroform	4.80	94.1
Dichloromethane	10.65	95.3
1% Cyclohexanol in Cyclohexane	—	23.0
10% Cyclohexanol in Cyclohexane	—	59.6
Nitrobenzene	36.10	93.4